

Research Article

Cerimetric Estimation Of Terazosin Hydrochloride In Bulk Drugs And In Pharmaceutical Formulations

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17 Aug 2024

Accepted: 19 Aug 2024

Published: 20 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Terazosin hydrochloride, Cerri ammonium sulphate, Ammonium thio-Cyanate, Spectrophotometer

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13351201

ABSTRACT

A simple, accurate and precise method was described for the determination of terazosin hydrochloride with cerium(IV) sulphate. The method is based on the oxidation of the terazosin hydrochloride by a known excess amount of cerium(IV) sulphate in acid medium and the unreacted cerium(IV) sulphate is treated with iron(II) sulphate, and the iron(III) sulphate produced is complexed with thiocyanate and measured at 480 nm, thereby permitting the determination of the amount of unreacted cerium(IV) sulphate.

INTRODUCTION

Terazosin hydrochloride dehydrate RS-1-(4-amino-6, 7- dimethoxy-2-quinazoliny)-4-[(tetrahydro-2-furanyl) carbonyl]- piperazine monohydrochloride [Fig.1] is α 1adrenoceptor blocker with a long lasting action. Various methods reported in literature for the determination of terazosin hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage forms which includes spectrophotometric method1-3, Fluorimetric Method4-6, Spectrophotometric and Spectrofluorimetric Method7, Potentiometric and

Fluorimetric Method8 HPLC Determination9, and, RP-HPLC Method10

Fig.1: Terazosin hydrochloride

The methods is based on the oxidation of the drug by a known excess amount of cerium(IV) sulphate in acid medium, and the determination of the

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

unreacted oxidant by spectrophotometry after treatment with iron(II) sulphate and complexing the iron(III) sulphate produced with thiocyanate. . The present investigation was undertaken with the aim of developing new, simple, rapid and accurate for the analysis of terazosin hydrochloride in bulk drug form and in various formulations. The reaction scheme is presented in Figure 3. The developed colour was stable for more than 30 min.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation

Spectronic 1000 plus UV Visible Spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched quartz cells was used for all spectral and absorbance measurements.

Reagents

All the chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade and solutions were prepared in double distilled water. AR grade hydrochloride acid was used in the present study.

Cerric ammonium sulphate(0.05M):

2.9826 g of AR ceric Ammonium Sulphate is dissolved in double distilled water and the resulting solution is made up to the mark in the 100 ml standard flask with double distilled water.

Ammonium ferrous sulphate Solution (0.02M):

0.7842 g of AR Ammonium Ferrous Sulphate is dissolved in distilled water and the solution is made up to the mark in the 100 ml standard flask with distilled water.

Ammonium Thio-Cyanate (1M):

7 g of AR Ammonium thio-cyanate is dissolved in double distilled water and the resulting solution is

made up to the mark in the 100 ml standard flask with double distilled water.

Preparation of standard terazosin hydrochloride solution:

50 mg of pure terazosin hydrochloride is dissolved in methanol and the volume is adjusted to 50 ml with methanol. The stock solution is further diluted to get working concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

DETECTION WAVELENGTH FOR LOPINAVIR AND TERAZOSIN HYDROCHLORIDE

The detection wavelength was determined by scanning the blood red solution in the range 380-620 nm using reagent blank. The overlain spectra (fig.2) were scanned and the wavelength was detected as 490 nm by using the following procedure. 1.0 ml of terazosin hydrochloride solution (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) is transferred into a standard flask and followed by the addition of 1 ml of 5 N hydrochloric acid and 1 ml cerium(IV) sulphate, and the overall volume are adjusted to 5 ml by adding a requisite volume of water. The flasks are let stand for 15 min with occasional shaking. Subsequently, 1ml of ammonium ferrous sulphate are added to each flask and the contents are mixed well. After 1 min, 3 ml of 1 M ammonium thiocyanate are added and the volume was made up to the mark, and the resultant solution gives blood red colour. The absorbance of the blood red colour solution is measured in the wavelength range of 380 to 620 nm, against the reagent blank.

Fig:2: Overlain spectrum of terazosin hydrochloride

From fig:2 shows the terazosin hydrochloride solution has maximum absorbance at 490 nm.

Assay procedure:

In each of a series of 10 ml standard flasks were placed 0.5-2.5 ml of terazosin hydrochloride followed by the addition of 1 ml of 5 M hydrochloric acid and 1 ml cerium(IV) sulphate, and the overall volume are adjusted to 5 ml by adding a requisite volume of water. The flasks are

let stand for 15 min with occasional shaking. Subsequently, 1 ml of ammonium ferrous sulphate was added to each flask and the contents are mixed well. After 1 min, 3 ml of 1 M ammonium thiocyanate are added and the volume was made up to the mark, and the absorbance is recorded at 490 nm against water blank. The concentration of the drug in an unknown solution is read from the calibration graph in the fig.3.

Fig:2. Calibration curve of terazosin hydrochloride

Linearity

A linear relation is found between absorbance and concentration in the ranges given in Table 1. In method B, Beer's law is obeyed in the inverse manner. The calibration graphs were described by the equation $Y = a + bX$ where $Y =$ absorbance,

$a =$ intercept, $b =$ slope and $X =$ concentration in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ obtained by the method of least squares. Correlation coefficients, intercepts and slopes for the calibration data are also presented in Table 1

Pharmaceutical Formulations:

Twenty tablets are weighed and ground into a fine powder. A portion of the powder equivalent to 100 mg of terazosin hydrochloride is accurately weighed into a 100 ml calibrated flask, 60 ml of water is added and the contents are shaken thoroughly for about 20 min to extract the drug.

The contents are diluted to the mark, mixed well and filtered using a quantitative filter paper to remove insoluble residue. An appropriate aliquot is subjected to analysis by spectrophotometry using the procedure described above. The results are given in Table.2.

Table.1: Optical characteristics of the proposed methods

Parameters	Proposed Method
λ_{max} (Nm)	490
Beer's Law Limit ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	50-250
Molar Absorptivity ($\text{L Mole}^{-1} \text{Cm}^{-1}$)	4.46×10^3
Sandell's Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g Cm}^{-2} / 0.001$ Absorbance Unit)	0.0224
Regression Equation ($Y = A + Bx$)	$Y=0.0025X+0.012$
Slope (B)	0.0043
Intercept (A)	0.002
Correlation Coefficient (R)	0.9999

* $Y = a+bX$, where Y is the absorbance and X concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$

Table.2 Assay of terazosin hydrochloride

Sample	*Labelled Amount (mg)	Amount Found (mg) \pm S.D	% of Label claim	C.V	t_{cal}
T ₁	5	199.98 \pm 0.04	99.98	0.9361	0.4784

*Average of five determinations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The method is based on the oxidation of terazosin hydrochloride with a known excess of cerium(IV) sulphate and the determination of the unreacted oxidant by spectrophotometry. This method is based on the oxidation of terazosin hydrochloride by a measured excess of cerium (IV) sulphate in HCl medium, reduction of the residual oxidant by a fixed amount of iron (II) and subsequent formation of iron (III)-thiocyanate complex, which is measured at 490 nm. When a fixed concentration of cerium (IV) sulphate is reacted with increasing concentrations of terazosin hydrochloride, there will be a proportional decrease in the concentration of the oxidant. The unreacted oxidant, when treated with a fixed concentration of iron (II) accounts for a proportional decrease in the iron (III) concentration. This is observed as a proportional

decrease in the absorbance of iron (III)-thiocyanate complex with the drug concentration, which formed the basis for the assay of drug. The Standard deviation, C.V and t_{cal} of the terazosin hydrochloride is calculated from five measurements of replicate samples. The values of Standard deviation, C.V and t_{cal} were shown in Table.6.3.2. The values of standard deviation and Coefficient of variation are low, indicates high accuracy and reproducibility of the method. The data of assay values of commercial formulations is subjected to statistical evaluation for student 't' test to study the proposed method. The calculated 't' values are less than 't' theoretical values with 4 ($n-1=5-1$) degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance indicate that there is no significant difference between proposed method and standard method. Commonly encountered excipients such as starch, talc, glucose, alginate

and stearate did not interfere in the proposed methods.

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HOW TO CITE: K. Nagaraja Setty, Sravanthi Chittela, K. Prabhavathi, Cerimetric Estimation Of Terazosin Hydrochloride In Bulk Drugs And In Pharmaceutical Formulations, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 3541-3545. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13351201>

